

ORGANIZATION OF ACCOUNTING AND REPORTING IN OPERATING SEGMENTS AT COTTON-TEXTILE CLUSTER ENTERPRISES

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Annotation: This article examines the issues of organizing accounting and reporting in operating segments in cotton-textile clusters, taking into account the experience of developed countries in this area.

Keywords: cotton-textile cluster, management accounting, segment, economic segment, geographic segment, segment accounting, segment reporting.

INTRODUCTION

The modernization and development of the economy of Uzbekistan requires further expansion of the integration of industry with agriculture, the structural transformation of the agro-industrial sector and the introduction of market management mechanisms.

The use of a cluster management system, which has a positive effect on the export orientation of enterprises and the responsibility for creating products with high added value, presupposes the creation of responsibility centers in the structure of an economic entity that are part of the cluster management system. For these purposes, according to International Financial Reporting Standard No. 8 “Operating Segments”, the enterprise and its structural divisions are divided into business (economic) and geographical segments. The rules and techniques adopted

for the preparation of segmental reporting should be included in the accounting policy of the organization (enterprise). [1]

Currently, in Navoi, Bukhara and other regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, clusters have been created on the basis of enterprises of the textile and light industry with the lease of reorganized enterprises for processing raw cotton, through the conclusion of direct agreements with farms that grow cotton raw materials, focused on the distribution of income according to economically justified norms from a single center. [2., p.1].

In connection with the organization of new types and forms of management in the economy, the role of management accounting and reporting for each operating segment is increasing. These prerequisites imply the development of methodological, organizational and practical issues of management segmental accounting and reporting for these innovations.

Literature review

A well-known economist, professor Karrieva Ya. in her study “Application of logistics in the innovative development of clusters in Uzbekistan” focuses on logistics for transport and logistics, customs and logistics, industrial and logistics, innovation and logistics clusters by type of activity. [3., p.3].

In our opinion, it is advisable to reclassify production and supply logistics in the control chain. In the chain of clusters of enterprise development, logistics needs to be grouped into legal, economic and social in the management system.

Researcher Z. Khakimov drew attention to the socio-economic efficiency of cluster formation in the textile industry and noted: “Textile enterprises need financial resources, skilled labor and high-tech laboratories for the formation and implementation of product, technological and marketing innovations. Businesses

do not have the ability to reach them all. In turn, the merger of enterprises into a cluster for the production of the final product will provide these opportunities. [4., p.4].

Research methodology

The scientific research focuses on the search results of foreign and domestic researchers on this issue. The article used methods such as statistical and sample observation, comparison, grouping and the method of evaluating experts.

Analysis and results

As evidenced by the advanced world experience, the cluster management system in the agricultural sector is a decisive factor in the development of agriculture. Therefore, at present, a cluster management method is being introduced in the agriculture of Uzbekistan, including cotton-textile clusters for the cultivation and processing of raw cotton.

The cluster's priority should be the integration of science, education and production. In fact, a cluster is an innovative method, and every work carried out in this system should be based on education, the achievements of science and technology. For these purposes, it is necessary to effectively organize the activities of Scientific Centers for the introduction of new innovative technologies and achievements of science, technology and education in cotton-textile clusters.

Next, we present an analysis of the report on the cultivation of raw cotton by cotton-textile clusters and on their production capacities in the Namangan region. (Table 1).

Table 1 - Report on the cultivation of raw cotton by cotton-textile clusters and their production capacity in Namangan region.

№	Name of cotton-textile clusters	The number of manufacturing enterprises, pieces.	Annual processing capacity:			
			Yarn. ton.	Harsh fabric thousand sq. meter	The cloth, ton.	Finished products, thousand pieces
1	“Art Soft Holding” LLC	9	6 400	8 000		52 000
2	“Toshbuloq teks” LLC	2	6 000			
3	“Namangan To`qimachi” LLC	10	7 200	20 000		1 500
4	“Uzteks Uchkurgan” LLC	2	7 000	10 000		
5	“Uchkurgan Textile” LLC	2	7 000			5 000
6	“Textile Finanse Namangan” LLC	3	12 000			
7	“Namangan paxta tekst” LLC	4	3 000		1 500	1 000
	TOTAL	32	48 600	38 000	1 500	59 500

Source. Developed by the author based on the reported economic and financial data of cluster enterprises in the Namangan region of Uzbekistan. [5]

As the analysis of the table shows, at 32 enterprises of the studied object, the annual processing capacity has different indicators. For example, the production of harsh fabric for the area is 38,000 thousand square meters. Finished products at the final stage of processing are 59,500 thousand pieces.

A deeper understanding of the nature of management segmental accounting and reporting at enterprises operating in a cluster management system is directly related to accounting management and production accounting.

Production accounting is timed to cost accounting and the determination of the cost of products (works, services). It contributes to the management of income and costs in the context of the business units of the enterprise. It should reflect in detail all issues related to the production and sale of products at the enterprise.

Table 2 - Operational report on the financial results of growing and processing raw cotton in clusters, million soums

№	Indicators	Total costs	Total income	Net profit
1	Total grown raw cotton products	74 836,4	96 522,0	21 685,7
2	Collection and storage of raw cotton	21 830,0	-	-
3	Cotton fiber processing	120 827,7	137 236,4	16 408,7
4	Processing of cotton seeds	4 253,0	19 635,0	15 382,0

Source. Developed by the author based on the reported economic and financial data of “NAVBAHOR TEKSTIL” LLC [6]

The use of this table in cotton-textile clusters allows you to quickly manage their activities. In particular, segment accounting and reporting of income and expenses of each segment, determination of their net profit based on transfer price principles is an important factor not only for increasing the material interest of each segment, but also for accounting for added value at the stages of their deep processing.

In countries with market economies, the procedure for the formation of segmental reporting in management accounting is regulated by International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) and has been in effect since 1993. At the same time, unlike production accounting, segmental accounting and reporting is involved in the horizontal management of the enterprise. This type of accounting complements production accounting with a very important point of its function, that is, in segmental accounting and reporting, income and expenses, financial results of a separate division of the enterprise are taken into account separately. This complements the gaps in vertically organized production accounting in enterprise management.

As Professor B. Khasanov notes: “a business segment is a separation of a certain part or a relatively independent subdivision of an enterprise for the purpose of delegating certain powers and responsibilities.

Management accounting consists of a set of different responsibility centers (business segments), taking into account the organizational structure of the enterprise.

A geographic segment is a separate component involved in the production of goods and services in a certain economic environment exposed to risk and profit, different from the risk and reward, specific to segments operating in other economic conditions ”[7., p. 165]

Currently, the procedure for preparing financial statements by segment for external users is regulated by the National Accounting Standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1 “Accounting Policy and Financial Reporting”. Paragraph 96 of that standard states: “When considering priorities for accounting policy functions for users, business leaders should consider assessing the risks and future cash flows of business entities. Accounting policies should include, but not be limited to:

- 96.17. determine the types of activities, geographical segments and the method of allocating costs between segments”[8., p.50]

Article 11 “Organization of accounting and reporting” of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan On amendments and additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the accounting” dated April 13, 2016 of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan states: “The head of the accounting entity is obliged to ensure:

- development of accounting policies, internal accounting and reporting systems;

- procedure for internal control". [9., p.3]

We believe that the costs and revenues of each operating segment should be documented in paper or electronic form using the accounting automation software, taking into account the specifics of the industry. Segment costs are costs that can be included directly in the aggregate of segment costs or reflected as part of an entity's total costs. (Table 3).

As the data in the table show, the cost of growing raw cotton products by the cluster method in 2020 in the limited liability company "OQ SAROY KLASTER" amounted to 315.0 billion soums. The main part of the costs falls on the cultivation of raw cotton, which amounted to 268.0 billion soums (85%), the costs of a ginning plant for processing raw cotton amounted to 25.0 billion soums (8%) and other expenses amounted to 20 billion soums (6.4%).

The total planned revenue of the cluster amounted to 363.7 billion soums, of which revenue from the sale of cotton fiber amounted to 274.6 billion soums (75.5%), the sale of cotton seeds - 80.3 billion soums (22.1%) , the sale of lint is expected to reach 7.6 billion soums (2.1%), and sales of down and beetle - 1.2 billion soums (0.3%).

In 2020, the net profit of the cotton gin of the cluster system is planned at 48.7 billion soums.

Table 3 - Report of economic indicators for the processing of grown raw cotton in “OQ SAROY KLASTER” LLC in 2020

N ^o	Indicators	Costs, billion soums	Share, %	Indicators	Income, billion soums	Share, %
1	Growing costs	268,0	85,0	Sale of cotton fiber	274,6	75,5
2	Costs of cotton ginning enterprises	25,0	8,0	Sale of cotton seeds	80,3	22,1
3	Shipping and storage costs	2,0	0,6	Sale of lint	7,6	2,1
4	Other costs	20,0	6,4	Selling fluff and ulyk	1,2	0,3
	Total costs:	315,0	100	Total income:	363,7	100
	Losses (-)			Profit (+)	48,7	

Source. Developed by the author based on the reported economic and financial data of “OQ SAROY KLASTER” LLC [10]

It should be noted that, according to international standards, the following general business costs should not be included in segment costs:

- costs for short-term and long-term financial investments (except for cases when they are the main activity of the segment);
- income tax (income);
- extraordinary expenses (force majeure).

Intra-production (segmental) reports should be based on the accounting, analytical and information base of financial and management accounting.

In order to form indicators of segmental reporting, it is necessary to organize reliable primary accounting in paper or electronic format. In this case, one should proceed from the technological features of the industry being taken into account. By maintaining segmental accounting and reporting, a comparative analysis of the costs and revenues of the enterprise segments is achieved.

Conclusion/recommendations

In conclusion, I would like to note that the role and importance of the cluster management system for the further development and modernization of the country's economy is invaluable. This economic structure will create opportunities and conditions for generalizing the chains of producers and consumers into a single logistics system and reaching the level of international exports.

Accelerating the transition to internationally recognized principles and standards of management accounting and reporting by operating segments requires deep research and implementation of their results in the methodological, regulatory and organizational framework for segment accounting and reporting.

References

1. International Financial Reporting Standard (IFRS) 8- “Operating Segments”. <https://finotchet.ru/articles/87>
2. “On measures for the further development of cotton-textile industries”. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan 230 from 18 march 2019 year. <https://lex.uz/docs/4245407>
3. Karrieva Ya. Primeneniye logistiki v innovatsionnom razvitii klasternoy deyatelnosti v Uzbekistane. Jurnal “Biznes-Ekspert” №6, 2019, s.3.
4. Xakimov Z. Sotsialno-ekonomicheskaya effektivnost formirovaniya klasterov v tekstilnoy promishlennosti. Jurnal “Biznes-Ekspert” №4, 2019g. s.4.
5. Reporting economic and financial data of cluster enterprises in the Namangan region of Uzbekistan.
6. Reporting economic and financial data of “NAVBAHOR TEKSTIL” LLC
7. Xasanov B.A., G‘aniyev Z.U., Muxammedova D.A. Boshqaruv hisobi. – T.: “Iqtisod- moliya”, 2018, 280 b.
8. National accounting standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1 “Accounting policies and financial reporting”. Registered in the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 14, 1998 No. 474. A set of national accounting standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent: Publishing house NORMA, 2018.- 368 p.
9. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on amendments and additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the accounting”. “Xalq so‘zi”, April 14, 2016. www.xs.uz
10. Reporting economic and financial data of “OQ SAROY KLASSTER” LLC